

**RESEARCH ON FACTORS AFFECTING THE MANEUVERABILITY
OF FOUR-WHEEL TRACTOR**

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Abstract: This study investigates the influence of trapezoidal transverse steering drive parameters on the maneuverability of high-traction tractors. The research focuses on the geometric and kinematic characteristics of the trapezoid configuration in the steering mechanism, including its impact on turning radius, steering efficiency, and overall vehicle stability during high-torque operations. A series of simulations and practical tests were conducted to analyze how variations in the trapezoidal drive parameters—such as angle, length, and alignment—affect the tractor's responsiveness and precision in low-speed and high-load conditions.

Keywords: tractor, turning, agility (turning ability), wheel, steering gear, steering trapezoid, turning radius, row spacing.

Introduction. Theoretical research into curvilinear motion of wheeled vehicles aims, above all, at receiving the mathematical equations of a motion trajectory. This issue is relevant in view of the trend of implementing into practice of conducting field operations an automated control over machine-tractor units (MTU). Vast majority of sown areas in the Republic is characterized by small contour and in this regard, significant part of the total tractor path is spent on turnarounds and laps. Therefore, the

most wide-spread properties of agriculture production are geometric restrictions on movement of machine and tractor units on turning lanes. In this regard, issue on minimizing the turning radius of the machine-tractor unit (MTU) is highest degree importance in solving such type of problems, especially in combination with reduction of unproductive time spent for implementation [1–6].

In recent years, activities have been carried out in world practice aimed on improving turning capacity of the tractor and reducing unproductive time spent on sheds when MTU is reoriented to implement working mode stroke in the opposite direction [2, 4]. Among these works, the most interesting is activities carried out at New Holland, at the Belarussian National Technical University, and at the Design and Technology Center for Agricultural Engineering (DTCAE).

Materials and methods of research

Thus, New Holland has developed new generation front traction, the distinguishing feature of which is that the Super SteerTM system used in it ensures, in addition to turning the pivot pin, also the front traction beam at a certain angle [1]. As a result, the angle of rotation of the guide wheels reaches up to 65° , which significantly reduces the radius of the tractor rotation. Undoubtedly, compared to conventional serial mechanisms, this mechanism contributes to a 30% reduction in turning lane width by reducing the turning radius. But, despite this, utilization of this mechanism does not provide rotation of a four-wheel tractor around one of its rear wheels.

Differing from New Holland company, a simple device - support wheel of piano-type was proposed at the Belarussian National Technical University in effort to increase the maneuverability of four-wheeled tractor. It can be installed on front hinged system of the tractor and will provide quick turnaround in almost at the same place, allowing several times to reduce unproductive time spent on turns, up to 20-30% of shift time [7].

Minimizing the radius of tractor rotation allows the leaning of its rear part to the support wheel, which can itself be installed in the direction of movement, and create turning moment by separately braking or driving the rear wheel propels ors in opposite

directions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSING

In contrast to the two previous ones, DTCAE has developed more compact assembly for turning a four-wheel tractor, based on a variable-trapezoid steering gear. A four-wheel tractor equipped with this mechanism rotates around one of its rear wheels with a minimum radius [8].

In real operating conditions of the curvilinear movement of the tractor, in which the side wheel drive is always present. However, we first consider in what proportions the angles of rotation of various wheels should be on the assumption: the wheels are rigid in the lateral direction, i.e. there is no skidding and the wheels roll in the plane of their rotation.

In our case, when the wheels of only one axle are controlled by a two-axle machine, we get:

$$\frac{CO}{BC} = ctg\alpha_2; \quad \frac{DO}{AD} = ctg\alpha_1,$$

$$AD = a = c \cdot \sin\alpha_2 = 2678 \cdot 0.5 = 1339mm;$$

$$DO = b = c \cdot \cos\alpha_2 = 2678 \cdot 0.866 = 2319.216mm;$$

$$CO = b + l_0 = 2319.216 + 1800 = 4119.216mm.$$

Subtracting from the first equality the second, mean $AD=BC$, we get;

$$ctg\alpha_2 - ctg\alpha_1 = \frac{l_0}{L} = \frac{1800}{2678} = 0.672,$$

Where l_0 – the distance between the axles of the pivot pin.

With the existing real ratios $\frac{l_0}{L}$ the difference in the angles of rotation of the inner and outer steered wheels is on average a fraction of a degree, so in most cases you can make calculations with sufficient accuracy for practice, take the average angle of rotation of the wheels and consider the so-called cycling turning scheme in which two wheels of the same axis as if united in one. The advantage of this scheme is a reduction by about 2 times the number of equations describing the movement of a

machine.

The turning radius, called the kinematic radius, is defined as

$$R = \frac{L}{\operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha_2 + \alpha_1}{2}} = \frac{L}{\operatorname{tg} \alpha} = \frac{2678}{\operatorname{tg} 35^\circ} = \frac{2678}{0.7} = 3825.7 \text{ mm}$$
$$R_2 = \frac{L}{\operatorname{tg} \alpha_2} = \frac{2678}{\operatorname{tg} 40^\circ} = \frac{2678}{0.839} = 3191.895 \text{ mm}$$
$$R_1 = \frac{L}{\operatorname{tg} \alpha_1} = \frac{2678}{\operatorname{tg} 30^\circ} = \frac{2678}{0.57735} = 4638.434 \text{ mm}$$

where L – the base of the tractor; α – the average angle of rotation of the driven wheels; O – the center of rotation of the tractor.

The determination of the turning radius of the tractor as the main operational indicator of the curvilinear motion of the machine-tractor unit (MTU) requires a number of additional systematic refinements. The classic assumptions about the kinematic motion of turning a wheeled tractor are based on a number of assumptions. The main assumptions are aimed at clarifying the concept of correctness of rotation, in which the wheels roll without sliding and there is no lateral wheel drive of the tractor.

As known, with the curvilinear movement of the tractor, an additional component of the lateral force increases, and tire slippage on the supporting surface occurs. In this case, the uniformity of motion is influenced not only by the speed of rotation, but also by the elastic and damping characteristics of the entire steering gear and tires. Consider the kinematic scheme of turning the tractor with rear driving and front driven wheels (Fig. 6). Let us assume that the tractor moves at a low constant speed, when the centrifugal force can be neglected.[9]

without a driver;

– to reduce unproductive power consumption for turning;

– to decrease additional cost in bringing the land on which the u-turns of MTU are performed into proper condition.

It is advisable to continue this work. It is necessary to study the impact on the accuracy of motion of such factors as the condition of soil, the relief of fields, weather conditions, sliding, skidding and the wheels slip in the curvilinear motion. Maintaining a stability of machines on sloping fields will make it possible to cultivate the land plots, which are considered unsuitable for farming. [10]

Conclusions

As you know, during wheel collision with an obstacle, hit occurs, the impact force arising from it through the lever of steering traction of steered wheel and cut by a symmetrical thrust acts on disc piston. Since the fluid in the cage is not compressed and the fluid does not instantly flow through the ditches into the other cavity of the cage, hit force is damped by them, thereby preventing possible wheel oscillations. In this case, fluid and spring plays the role of damper, and thereby preventing the possibility of wheel oscillations, ensures the reliability of entire steering trapezoid.

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